

#10

Evaluation & Impact Assessment

DIAGNOSTIC CHECKLIST AS A LEARNING TOOL FOR DEVELOPMENTAL EVALUATION (DE)

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>ENGAGING & INCENTIVISING APPLYING CREATING ADDRESSING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>In nascent stages of an interactive project/initiative, and/or at junctures prior to creative, inventive, co-creative multi-actor work.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Whole multi-actor group, small to medium. Most co-creation occurs in relatively small groups, which may amalgamate to a larger group as necessary.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>No technical skills required, although the language can be specialist at times. Language can be made more generic if required.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>1-3 hours initially (depending on the length of associated discussions).</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Requires basic materials, little or no cost.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools # 19, 20, 21.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source:
www.betterevaluation.org

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Assess whether Developmental Evaluation (DE) is appropriate for a project/initiative. using three diagnostic checklists
- Use the checklists at individual or group level, to raise consciousness of very important features and dynamics of interactive innovation, which should be in place in all interactive innovation projects.
- Evaluate existing features and dynamics of interactive innovation in light of the questions posed in the checklists; and identify areas for improvement as necessary.
- Use the results (and periodic use) of the checklists to instigate a process of continuous improvement.

Image source: [Alexandr Podvalny on Pexels.com](https://www.pexels.com/photo/young-green-plant-growing-in-soil/)

Background and Logic

Developmental Evaluation is described as 'an approach to understanding the activities of a program operating in dynamic, novel environments with complex interactions' (Norman, 2011¹). DE is in many ways inherent to interactive innovation and many of the tools in the current handbook are inspired by DE approaches. This DE diagnostic checklist asks facilitators/organisers/implementers of interactive innovation very important questions that challenge them in relation to their nature of their project/initiative and how it is operated – does it (and its dynamics) really qualify as interactive innovation?

This valuable diagnostic tool was developed by Mark Cabaj². It assesses projects/initiatives or development situations in general through three main lenses. The first relates to the context or subject matter of the project/initiative, does it really accommodate adaptiveness, a necessary condition for innovation? The second concerns those leading in a project/initiative, are they working in an adaptive way, facilitating co-creation? The third lens relates to those involved in interactive innovation and assesses the extent to which they are willing to work in an adaptive way, and to respond positively to information and assessments that seek to improve how they work. This last lens relates to how the tools presented in handbooks such as this one are used – how willing are participants to use tools such as those contained in this handbook, and to use the insights & learnings generated to positively improve their practices? In all, the three lenses entail questions that are challenging for even the most successful interactive innovation projects. The aim of this tool is to provoke a reflexive process where participants strive to be more compatible with DE. Used periodically, the tool can be used to benchmark progress against previous results and to create a culture where actors proactively create optimal conditions for interactive innovation.

It is important to note that the author of the tool suggests that the diagnostic checklists operate as three 'stage gates' i.e. if the context (assessed by checklist 1) is deemed incompatible with DE, there is little point in pursuing to the next checklist (2), which assesses the group, and even less point in progressing to checklist 3. This is logical when it comes to the assessment of projects/initiatives in general.

However, as multi-actor interactive innovation projects are generally formed in relation to a topic/context that *requires* an adaptive approach, such projects using this tool are highly likely to be found compatible with DE using checklist 1. Furthermore, we use the checklists as a tool to *learn about DE* and the conditions for DE. Checklist 1 is valuable, in that respect, because it can assess weaknesses & strengths in how adaptive the innovation context is, identifying areas for development (where possible). Furthermore, it attunes participants to leverage adaptiveness of the innovation context. Similarly, where checklist 2 is concerned, even if the adaptive capacity of the group is found to be low, we suggest progressing to use checklist 3 nonetheless. Learnings arise from these checklists regarding the conditions that make DE suitable (which are also essential conditions for interactive innovation). Therefore, where use of this tool for interactive innovation projects/initiatives (specifically) is concerned, we suggest using all three diagnostic checklists and for participants to identify learnings from all three.

Materials

- Three diagnostic checklists (multiple copies and/or versions shown on screen and/or large poster prints)
- Stickers (small size, any shape, generic)
- Pens
- Flipchart paper
- Sticky-notes
- Thick black markers

1 <https://censemaking.com/2011/11/19/what-is-developmental-evaluation/>

2 <https://www.tamarackcommunity.ca/library/developmental-evaluation-diagnostic-checklist>

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Step 1: Preparation

- Explain the purpose, logic and background.
- Optionally, distribute copies of the three diagnostic checklists (below) in advance of the meeting to allow participants to become familiar with the content.

Step 2: Complete the Diagnostic Checklists

- Each of the checklists are completed in turn and discussed, rather than moving on to the next checklist:
- Issue the checklist individually to participants, with pens available.
- Place a large (flipchart size) copy of the checklist on a board/table
 - » OR data project the checklist on a large whiteboard
 - » OR print the checklist on size A3 paper.
- Allow participants approximately 20 mins to read and complete the checklist (individually and privately). Note: the facilitator may opt to allocate less or more or less time, depending on the experience of the group with such checklists).
- Issue stickers to each participant (one sticker per question on the checklist).
- Ask them to approach the board/table/whiteboard and select their chosen answers by placing a sticker in the field of their chosen answer OR hand around the checklist on a A3 sheet and ask participants to add their stickers, indicating their chosen answers.
- The facilitator calculates the score.

Step 3: Discuss the Results of Each Checklist in Turn and Identify Ideas/Strategies for Improvement

- A sheet of flipchart paper is placed on a stand/board, with the following topic banner 'Checklist 1/2/3- ideas for improvement'.
- Sticky notes and thick black markers are issued to participants
- A discussion is facilitated in relation to each individual score (scored collectively):
- Take the 'tips' below into account when discussing the scores – some questions are more relevant to certain actors than others.
- Using the following types of prompting questions to facilitate the discussion:
 - » Why do you think the majority has chosen this answer (where relevant)?
 - » What experiences or incidents do you think explain this particular answer?
 - » What about these other answers (minority responses, where relevant)- do they provide a different view? What is that view?
 - » Does anyone have any ideas to improve how we are operating according to the results of this question (each question in turn)? Can anyone think of any strategies for improvement?
- Ideas are written on sticky notes by participants (with assistance where necessary), and placed on the flip chart sheet with topic banner.
- The overall score, calculated the facilitator, is discussed, using the following types of prompting questions:
 - » How suitable is our context/group to DE?
 - » Considering our discussion of the individual questions, can you identify any of the ideas or strategies you identified as particularly important?
- Make a note of the strategies that are considered particularly/important e.g. by circling them in marker, or by moving them to another piece of flipchart paper, with an identifying topic banner (citing the particular checklist under discussion).

Step 4: Use of the Diagnostic Checklists as Tools for Formative Learning and Assessment

- The completed checklists provide a score regarding suitability of the project's/initiative's context, leaders, and participants to DE. Because DE is integral to interactive innovation, the completed checklists evaluate important dynamics in the interactive innovation process.
- The nature of the questions in the checklists attune participants to very important questions relating to necessary conditions for interactive innovation, making them more conscious of the need to be proactive in creating those conditions. The process of completing the checklists, thus, is a learning process in itself, building reflexivity.
- It is important to record the suggestions from participants with regard to improving conditions for interactive innovation, and to revisit the suggestions and progress towards achieving them at project/initiative meetings.
- The exercise can be repeated periodically, assessing changing dynamics and identifying further suggestions for improvement.
- When undertaken repeatedly, the results of previous diagnostic checklists may assess progress or otherwise, and outstanding suggestions for improvement may be identified and prioritised for implementation where necessary.

Checklist 1 (focused on context). Source Mark Cabaj, [Better Evaluation](#). Original pdf accessible [here](#).

Is it a developmental situation?

TIP: The higher the score (+), the better conditions for interactive innovations

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1 The challenge we want to address is difficult to define (e.g. poverty)	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
2 There are multiple, often unknown, causes underlying the challenge that interact in difficult-to-predict ways.	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
3 The stakeholders involved (directly and indirectly) have diverse values, interests and perspectives.	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
4 The group is experimenting with different ways to turn their idea 'theory of change' into reality (e.g. a grant program, a training course) but this idea or theory is not yet developed or tested)	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
5 The results of our efforts (types, scale, speed) are (apt to be) uncertain and/or unpredictable.	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
6 The context in which the group is operating (e.g. funding, partners, demographics, stakeholders) is rapidly changing and may require the group to make changes to their work.	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
7 The group is working in multiple different contexts or across multiple scales (e.g. organisation, city, region, states) requiring some 'adaption' or intervention.	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
Sub-total					
Total					

Results

-11 to -14	Accountability Situation	Your intervention is well developed and may be working in a stable environment. You may be seeking evaluation feedback for accountability which aims to find out if you are implementing it with fidelity to a well laid out and proven model.	TIP: Main message here is 'implementing to a well laid out and proven model'
-6 to -10	Effective Situation	Your intervention is very well developed. You may also be seeking evaluation feedback to judge the model's effectiveness (aka summative evaluation)	TIP: Main message here is that the project/initiative is decided and requires validation rather than experimentation
+6 to -5	Improvement Situation	Your intervention is relatively stable and/or operating in a stable environment. You may be seeking evaluation feedback to improve the model (aka formative evaluation)	TIP: Main message here is that the project/initiative and its context is more or less decided but open to modification
+7 to +14	Developmental Situation	Your intervention is developing or emerging. You may be seeking evaluation feedback to develop the model.	TIP: Main message here is that the project/initiative is developing/evolving/in the process of innovation. Very suited to DE & interactive innovation.

Checklist 2 (focused on project/initiative leaders). Source Mark Cabaj, [Better Evaluation](#). Original PDF accessible [here](#).

TIP: The higher the score (+), the better conditions for interactive innovations

Do You Have Adaptive Capacity?

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1 We have a history of innovation and tackling complex issues	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
TIP: Important to note that newly established groups may not have a 'history' but may be 'comfortable' with innovation etc. Change if needed.					
2 We are comfortable with ambiguity, uncertainty and the tension of adaptive work	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
3 We are motivated to try something new and committed to a systemic process of innovation	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
4 We have sufficient resources to carry out its work, and can invest more if/when promising new avenues emerge.	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
Tip: Instead of 'can invest more', can substitute with 'can investigate more'					
5 We are willing to "learn-by-doing", allowing the intervention to emerge over time, rather "plan the work and work the plan"	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
Tip: Particularly critical where interactive innovation is concerned!					
6 We have the flexibility and authority to change the emerging intervention to reflect new learnings and shifts in environment.	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
Tip: Particularly critical where interactive innovation is concerned!					
7 We have permission and room to make "safe-to-fail" errors and mistakes in search of what does and does not work.	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
Tip: Particularly critical where interactive innovation is concerned!					
8 We are more interested in learning and getting results, than being perceived to be "right"	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
Tip: Particularly critical where interactive innovation is concerned!					
9 We have time and patience to experiment with new approaches and generate results.	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
Tip: Particularly critical where interactive innovation is concerned!					
Sub-total					
Total					

Results

-9 to -18	Non-existent	Your group is working with fairly rigid context which does not allow it to engage in an authentic process of exploration and innovation
0 to -8	Low	Your group's ability to work adaptively is very limited. You should proceed with extreme care (if at all) and work hard at addressing your weak areas before or during the innovation process.
1 to 11	Good	Your group has an adaptive capacity to move forward, though some areas may need extra attention before or during the innovation process.
12 to 18	Excellent	Your group is in an excellent position to innovate and/or work on complex issues.

Checklist 3 (focused on wider participants in innovation).

Source Mark Cabaj, [Better Evaluation](#). Original PDF accessible [here](#).

TIP: The higher the score (+), the better conditions for interactive innovations

Are You Ready for Learning and Evaluation?

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1 We are hungry for evaluative feedback on your work	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
2 We understand that we all operate with cultural and cognitive biases which “shape” the way we interpret the feedback on our work	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
3 We have a history of gathering, analysing and making sense of data (or fully prepared to going forward)	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
TIP: Some actors will have more experience than others in this area - that shouldn't be perceived as a problem - important to note during facilitation					
4 We have a culture of curiosity, enquiry and critical reflection	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
5 We have demonstrated commitment to “data based” decision making	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
Tip: See above comment. Not relevant to all participants, which should not be perceived as negative. However, in a multi-actor group, it is useful to have some actors with these skills. The overall (group) score should take this into account. How did the actors to whom these questions are relevant score the questions?					
6 We've had positive experiences in evaluations (and evaluators) in the past	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
Tip: See above comment. Not relevant to all participants, which should not be perceived as negative. However, in a multi-actor group, it is useful to have some actors with these skills. The overall (group) score should take this into account. How did the actors to whom these questions are relevant score the questions?					
7 We understand and broadly support developmental evaluation	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
8 We are prepared to commit time and resources to developmental evaluation	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
9 We have someone (external or internal) in the role of developmental evaluator	+2	+1	0	-1	-2
Tip: or, actor/s willing to take the role?					
Sub-total					
Total					

Results

-6 to -18	Poor	You require significant work to improve the conditions for developmental evaluation before you move forward
-5 to 0	Low	Your group readiness for developmental evaluation is limited. Proceed with caution. Address short-comings before you begin and/or intentionally approach the work moving forward as an opportunity to strengthen your capacity for developmental evaluation. Be prepared for the fact that you may choose to discontinue developmental evaluation mid-way through the process, or you may say you are doing developmental evaluation when you are in fact using evaluation in more of a formative or summative mode.
1 to +10	Medium	Your group is sufficiently ready for developmental evaluation to begin, though it should keep on an eye on its weaker areas of readiness and/or identify measures to strengthen them as you proceed.
+11 to +14	High	Your group is an excellent candidate for developmental evaluation.

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